

Determination of Lactic Acid by Ceric Sulphate Oxidation

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A procedure is described for the volumetric determination of lactic acid or lactate, based on its oxidation by ceric sulphate in presence of sulphuric acid at 115° to acetaldehyde which is aerated and estimated by oxidising it with alkaline iodine solution. The procedure may be adopted for evaluating 0.6 mg. to 70 mg. of lactic acid. The interference caused by salts of other organic acids and certain organic compounds has also been investigated. Analytical precision is to 0.5% or better for 6 to 70 mg. of lactic acid, whereas for smaller amounts the error does not exceed 2%.

Several workers¹ have used potassium permanganate or potassium dichromate as an oxidant for lactic acid. In the present communication, use of ceric sulphate as an oxidant has been described. Although the redox potential of ceric sulphate is very near that of acidified dichromate, it has been shown by several workers² that this oxidant forms complexes in acid solutions. Krishna and Tewari³ in a kinetic study of the oxidation of lactic acid in ceric sulphate have shown that with increase in sulphuric acid content of the solution, the rate of oxidation diminishes. This is probably due to formation of complex ions like $Ce(SO_4)_3^{2-}$, $Ce(SO_4)_4^{2-}$. The acetaldehyde evolved escapes unoxidised in presence of low concentrations of ceric sulphate, whereas with dichromate and permanganate, it is likely to be partly oxidised to acetic acid if the aeration is not very fast. Hence the methods already devised by previous workers with dichromate and permanganate depend for their accuracy on certain critical conditions. The advantage with ceric sulphate is its freedom from such conditions. This is because ceric sulphate is not very soluble in solutions of sulphuric acid weaker than 0.5 *N*. The mixture of 2 g. of ceric sulphate and 20 ml of 0.1*N*-H₂SO₄, which was mostly used as the oxidant in these experiments, probably furnished a very low concentration of ceric ions and this remained constant; as the ceric ions were consumed, more of the solid dissolved. The oxidation potential of ceric sulphate is 1.43 ± 0.05 volts in 1 to 8*N* H₂SO₄ at 25°, but in the present experiments the acid concentrations were mostly between 0.05 and 0.15 *N*. A clear solution of the salt was never obtained and the oxidising mixture contained ceric sulphate and basic ceric sulphate.

Further, this mixture of ceric sulphate fails to act on many other organic compounds and thus makes the method selective. No mention has been made by Kolthoff *et al.*⁴, and

1. Furth and Charnass, *Biochem. Z.*, 1911, **27**, 199; Bellet, *Compt. rend. soc. Biol.*, 1913, **74**, 900; Hansen, *Tids. Kem. Bergv.*, 1925, **5**, 172, 187; Galvao *et al.*, *Arquiv. inst. Biol. (Sao paulo)*, 1938, **9**, No. 4, 39-50 (in English), 49-50; Leone and Tafuri, *Ann. Chim. appl.*, 1925, **15**, 206.
2. Smith, "Cerate Oxidimetry", G. F. Smith & Co., Ohio, p. 20, 1942; Moore and Anderson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, **66**, 1476; King and Pandou, *ibid.*, 1953, **75**, 3063; Hargreaves and Sutcliffe, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1955, **51**, 1105; Hardwick and Robertson, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1951, **29**, 828.
3. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 3097.
4. "Volumetric Analysis", Vol. III, Interscience Publishers, pp. 158-163, 1957.

Smith⁵ to the use of ceric compounds for oxidising lactic acid. Hence this field has been explored for new possibilities in cerate oxidimetry. In the procedure described here, pure lactic acid or lactate solution is allowed to react with hot ceric sulphate in presence of sulphuric acid in accordance with the equation:

Acetaldehyde produced during the reaction is recovered by a stream of air blown through the reaction mixture and collecting it in ice-cold water. The aldehyde is estimated by oxidising it with sodium hypiodite⁶.

EXPERIMENTAL

Iodine (0.1*N*, 0.02 *N*, and 0.01*N*) solutions and starch (1% aq. soln.) of A. R. quality, sodium thiosulphate (0.1*N* and 0.01*N* soln.) and sodium hydroxide (ca. 1.0 and 0.1*N* soln.) of Merck's variety, lactic acid (0.1*M*), and ceric sulphate of B. D. H., and sulphuric acid of approximately 1.0 and 0.1*N* solutions were used.

The lactic acid solutions were standardised by titrating against a standard solution 0.1*N*-NaOH(carbonate-free), using phenolphthalein as indicator.

Procedure.—Pure lactic acid (5-10 ml) or a lactate solution (containing 10 to 70 mg. of lactic acid) was pipetted into a 100-ml r.b. flask. To this 20 ml of 0.1 *N*-H₂SO₄ solution and 2.0 g. of solid ceric sulphate were added. A rubber cork with two glass tubes, one for aeration and the other acting as a delivery tube, was fitted to the flask. The free end of the delivery tube was connected to three 150-ml conical flasks as receivers, kept in an ice-bath, each containing about 70ml distilled water. The last receiver was connected to a filter pump through a filter flask. The r. b. flask was heated for 45 min. in a mobil oil thermostat maintained at 115°. During this period slow aeration was maintained. Later the contents of the three receivers were transferred to a 250-ml measuring flask and the volume was made to the mark with water. This acetaldehyde solution was evaluated iodimetrically⁶ by pipetting 100ml of the solution into a 300-ml iodine flask and treating it with 0.1*N* iodine solution (20 ml). The contents were made alkaline with 1.0*N*-NaOH (1.5 ml). The alkali, added dropwise from a burette with swirling of the flask after each addition, was insufficient to convert all the iodine to sodium hypiodite. This free iodine was allowed to remain for 45 min. in the reaction mixture, as described in Bose's procedure⁶. The contents were then acidified with 1.0*N*-H₂SO₄ (ca. 2 ml) and the liberated iodine was titrated with 0.1*N* sodium thiosulphate solution, using a starch solution (1 ml) as indicator. A blank was carried out with distilled water.

Evaluation of Small Amounts of Lactic Acid.—The same procedure as above was adopted with a slight modification for estimating minute quantities (0.6 mg. to 6.0 mg.) of lactic acid or its salts. Here the acetaldehyde was oxidised to iodoform⁷ and not acetic acid. A

5. Smith, *op.cit.*, p. 88-117.

6. This *Journal*, 1957, **34**, 739.

7. Bose, *Anal. Chem.*, 1958, **30**, 1526.

lactic acid solution (0.6-6.0 mg., 10 ml) was oxidised by 2.0 g. of ceric sulphate in 0.1*N*-H₂SO₄ (20 ml) for 45 min. at 115°. The acetaldehyde, obtained by aeration, was treated with 0.02*N* iodine solution (50 ml) and a 0.1*N*-NaOH solution (25 ml), added quickly with vigorous swirling. The alkali used here was in excess of that required for converting all the iodine to hypoiodite and consequently acetaldehyde was converted to iodoform. After allowing the reaction mixture to stand for 30 min., the contents were acidified with 1*N*-H₂SO₄ (3 ml) and the liberated iodine titrated with 0.01*N* sodium thiosulphate, using the starch solution (2ml) as indicator. For judging the end point precisely, the solution containing iodine was first rendered colorless with thiosulphate and then back-titrated with 0.01*N* iodine solution to a slight blue colour. The amount of iodine solution used was deducted from thiosulphate reading. A blank was carried out under identical conditions, using 100 ml of distilled water instead of acetaldehyde solution and the blue colour finally obtained was compared with the assay mixture.

(1 ml of 0.01 *N*-I₂ ≡ 0.15 mg. of lactic acid)

The results of analysis of pure solutions of lactic acid and sodium lactate (Table I) reveal that the present procedure has an analytical precision to 0.5% or better for 6-70 mg. of lactic acid and for smaller amounts (0.7-2.0 mg.) the error does not exceed 2%.

TABLE I

Amount of lactic acid.		%Error.
Present.	Found.	
69.42 mg.	69.74 mg.	+0.46
36.67	36.67	±0.00
13.88	13.82	-0.43
6.94	6.97	+0.43
2.08	2.05	-0.96
1.38	1.36	-1.44
0.69	0.70	+2.02
Lactic acid in sodium lactate.		
36.67	36.56	-0.29
6.94	6.90	-0.57
1.38	1.40	+1.44

Effect of Changing the Concentration of Sulphuric Acid and Amount of Ceric Sulphate.—It was observed that on increasing the concentration of H₂SO₄ while keeping the other conditions same, the rate of oxidation diminished considerably and the time of heating for completion of the reaction increased. This is in confirmation with the findings of Krishna and Tewari³, who have stated that the rate of oxidation of lactic acid by ceric sulphate is inversely proportional to the square of concentration of H₂SO₄ present. In Fig. 1 a graph (curve I) has been drawn showing the effect of change in initial concentration of H₂SO₄ on the amounts of lactic acid estimated in 45 min., using a 115° bath. Good results were obtained when the initial concentration of H₂SO₄ was between 0.05*N* and 0.15*N*.

The amount of ceric sulphate was varied from 0.5 to 6.0 g., keeping the concentration of H_2SO_4 at 0.07*N* and a graph was drawn (Fig. 1, curve II). It was found that 1.5 to 2.0 g. of ceric sulphate provided the best results.

FIG. 1. Dependence of the value of lactic acid on H_2SO_4 conc. (curve I) and the amount of ceric sulphate (curve II). Lactic acid added=36.6 mg.

FIG. 2. Effect of dilution (curve I) and the time of heating (curve II) on the lactic acid evaluated.

Effect of Dilution of Reaction Mixture and Time of Heating.—Keeping other conditions constant, the effect of addition of water was studied. Lactic acid (36.6 mg., 5 ml) mixed with ceric sulphate (2 g.) and 0.1 *N*- H_2SO_4 (20 ml) was heated for 45 min. after diluting with varying quantities of water. The effect of dilution of the reaction mixture on the lactic acid estimated has been shown in Fig. 2, curve I. Water to the extent of 20 ml can be added without affecting the results.

The study on the effect of changing the heating time showed that heating for 40 to 50 min. provided the best results, as depicted in Fig. 2, curve II.

Interferences.—Numerous carboxy-acid salts and other compounds were mixed with lactic acid and the interferences studied. The results are recorded in Table II. Oxalic, acetic, benzoic, formic, propionic, succinic, palmitic, adipic, and butyric acids did not interfere when present in equimolar proportions.

DISCUSSION

The method is thus found to be an elegant one with good precision and free from interferences by many organic acids and salts. Microquantities can also be estimated fairly accurately. A large number of organic compounds⁶ can be estimated by oxidising with excess of acidified ceric sulphate solution and evaluating the unused oxidant. The disadvantage of this process is that it can be applied to pure solutions only. In the present proced-

6. Kolthoff *et al.*, *op. cit.*, pp. 160-67.

ture, instead of estimating ceric sulphate, one of the products of oxidation has been collected and estimated. Therefore the method thus becomes a selective one. It is also not interfered by the presence of small quantities of lactide (up to 5%) with lactic acid sample.

TABLE II

Lactic acid added = 36.67 mg.

Lactic acid solution (10 ml) + 0.1 *N*-H₂SO₄ (20ml) + ceric sulphate (2g).

Expt. No.	Substance added.	Lactic acid found.	% Error.
A. No interference.			
1	Sodium acetate (40 mg.)	36.56 mg.	— 0.3
2	„ adipate „	35.71	— 2.6
3	„ benzoate „	36.56	— 0.3
4	„ formate „	36.56	— 0.3
5	„ oxalate „	36.56	— 0.3
6	„ palmitate „	35.99	— 1.8
7	„ propionate „	37.12	+ 1.2
8	„ succinate „	35.99	— 1.8
9	Calcium butyrate „	37.12	+ 1.2
10	„ gluconate „	37.68	+ 2.7
B. Interference.			
11	Benzaldehyde (0.2 g.)	53.28	+ 45.3
12	Ethanol (0.7 g.)	54.55	+ 48.7
13	Formaldehyde (0.4 g.)	130.00	+ 254.5
14	Glucose (40 mg.)	39.61	+ 8.0
15	Methanol (0.7 g.)	61.38	+ 67.5
16	Potassium citrate (40 mg.)	29.81	— 23.5
17	„ tartrate „	25.31	— 30.9
18	Sodium aminoacetate „	32.02	— 10.2
19	„ fumarate „	25.11	— 31.5
20	„ malate „	30.82	— 15.9
21	„ maleate „	25.11	— 31.5
22	„ malonate „	34.03	— 7.1
23	„ phenylacetate „	33.47	— 8.7
24	„ salicylate „	16.31	— 55.5
25	Salicylaldehyde (0.2 g.)	Interferes very smuch.	

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